

A Feasibility Study on Offering Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) in Sulu State College for 2018-2023

Frissida A. Daud, MAN, Ph.D.¹
1 – School of Nursing, Sulu State College

Publication Date: May 23, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15653569

Abstract

The study examined into the feasibility of reviving the offering of Bachelor of Science in Nursing in Sulu State College (SSC) for the School year 2018-2019 and beyond. It also looked into their budgetary profile expected and how this can support the operation of the school for 2018-2023, a Time Series Analysis was utilized. The study is used as basis for administrative planning and decision whether to reestablish the program or not. The study made use of descriptive design through documentary analysis and survey of respondents from potential students who are willing to enroll in the program at SSC. The examination and analysis of compliance in various areas crucial to the operation of the program was based from CMO 15, s. 2017 guidelines in terms of administration; faculty; library; laboratory and facilities; enrollment; curriculum; and budget. Based from the examination and analysis, the re-establishment of offering of Bachelor of Science

in Nursing (BSN) in Sulu State College for the School year 2018-2019 and beyond is feasible and viable. Given the overall total profitability ratio for the Five Years (2018-2023) of 16.83%, the School of Nursing can move from significant losses in the initial years to substantial profits by the end of the period indicating that their financial performance can achieve operational efficiency and financial success. Further, it is recommended, re-establishment of offering of BSN in Sulu State College for the School year 2018-2019 and beyond is feasible and sustainable, considering the availability of its existing infrastructures and resources, their significant milestone to revive the program to operate independently to continue to provide an affordable, accessible, quality nursing education thru challenge-driven commitment (CDC) in the pursuit of being a catalyst of change for health human resource development (HHRD) and socio-economic development locally, regionally, nationally and as far as globally.

Keywords: *nursing education, program feasibility, higher education sustainability, health human resource development, BSN curriculum compliance*

Introduction

Sulu State College has started its operation in the school year 2004-2005 under the umbrella of the Arts and Sciences Department of Sulu State College. In June 17, 2005, a board Resolution No. 33, s. 2005 authorized the president to enter into a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) with Western Mindanao State University (WMSU) regarding the offering of a course in Associate in Health Sciences Education (AHSE) effective 2004-2005. Hence then, the nursing program at SSC has been in consortium with WMSU College of Nursing (WMSU-CN) in 2005-2018.

However, Sulu State College has been issued CMO dated February 18, 2013 through CHED Resolution No. 414 – 2012 which was based from Commission En Banc (CEB) Resolution NO. 353-2012, and considering that the institution obtained 30% and below performance in the Nurse Licensure Examination from 2008 to 2010, the Commission further approved the immediate phase-out of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program of Sulu State College effective AY 2013-2014. But, due to the delayed communication and coordination received by SSC which only occurred in May 2014, SSC in coordination with WMSU-CN was able to accept freshmen students who are currently candidates for Graduation this March 2018, and considered the last batch of the program in Consortium with WMSU-CN.

However, since SSC NLE Performance in the NLE from 2014-2016 has been remarkably improved with a rating of 59.15% and given a remark of complied during the Unified CHED-PRC BON Monitoring and Evaluation conducted on May 30, 2017 @ CHED-OPSD office, Manila, and considering the availability of its existing infrastructures and resources, it is very significant milestone to revive the program to operate independently to continue to provide an affordable, accessible, quality nursing education thru Challenge-Driven Commitment (CDC) in the pursuit of being a catalyst of change for Health Human Resource Development (HHRD) and Socio-Economic Development locally, regionally, nationally and as far as globally.

Moreover, added to this remarkable improvement, on April 27, 2018, the Board of Trustees of Sulu State College during its regular meeting in Davao City has unanimously approved and accepted the offering of BSN program at Sulu State College with reference to the INITIAL permit (ARMM) No. PC04-CC10—1-16 s. 2018 given for the First Curricular year 2018-2019 issued by CHED-ARMM during its actual visitation on March 24, 2018 at Sulu State College. Furthermore, it was from these, the preparation of the Nursing operation and undertakings for the 1st Semester, SY: 2018-2019 were based. Therefore, it is with this developmental milestone, this feasibility study has been conducted.

Statement of the Problem

The study examined into the feasibility of reviving the offering of Bachelor of Science in Nursing at Sulu State College for the School year 2018-2019 along different parameters.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What are the qualifications of Sulu State College in offering BSN program in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Administration;
 - 1.2. Faculty;
 - 1.3. Library;
 - 1.4. Laboratory and facilities;
 - 1.5. Enrollment
 - 1.6. Curriculum; and
 - 1.7. Budget?

2. What budgetary profile is expected and how this can support the operation of the school for 2018-2023?

Methodology

The study made use of descriptive research design and utilized documentary analysis to generate data along the different resources such as administration, faculty, library, laboratory and facilities, enrollment, curriculum, and budget. Data presented in this research were sourced out from the SSC units dated 2013-2018 primarily School of Nursing Office, Planning Office, Admission Office, Human Resource Management, and Accounting Units. Through the help of the admission office, a survey was conducted to gather data on the potential enrolment to the BSN program at SSC. Furthermore, generated data on budgetary profile expected and how this can support the operation of the school for 2018-2023, a Time Series Analysis was utilized. Time series analysis allows for: a) trend analysis: identifying long-term increases or decreases in collection, expenses, and income over the years; b) descriptive statistics: calculating measures such as the annual growth rates, average collection, expenses, and income over the period, and the variability of these figures; and c) financial ratios: analyzing the relationship between collection, expenses, and income (e.g., profitability ratios like income as a percentage of collection) (Box et al, 2018; Moore et al, 2017 & Gitman et al 2017). The most direct and informative profitability ratio utilized in this study is the Income as a Percentage of Collection, also known as the Net Profit Margin with corresponding formula: $\text{Income as a Percentage of Collection} = (\text{Collection}/\text{Income}) \times 100\%$.

Results and Discussion

Qualifications of SSC-SN

The following are the qualifications of the SSC-SN in terms of reestablishment of offering BSN program along the different resources such as administration, faculty, library; laboratory and facilities, enrollment, curriculum; and budget which SSC strives to conform and adhere to the Policies, Standards, and Guidelines in CMO 15, s. 2017.

1.1 . Administration

The SSC-SN will be administered by one (1) full-time dean with the following qualifications such as a Filipino citizen; b. Registered Nurse in the Philippines with current and valid PRC ID; c. Holder of Master's degree in Nursing (MAN) conferred by a college or university duly recognized by the Commission on Higher Education; d. Has at least one (1) year experience of clinical practice and a total of at least five (5) years of experience in teaching, administration and supervision of nursing education; e. Physically and mentally fit; f. Of good moral character; g. Has no other teaching assignments or administrative functions in other public/private institutions or higher education institutions; h. Member of accredited professional nursing organization of good standing; i. An active member of good standing of the Association of Deans of Philippine College of Nursing (ADPCN); and, j. Have a duly notarized employment contract of at least one (1) academic year renewable annually that specifies the academic rank.

1.2. Faculty

The available faculty members of the School of Nursing, as it ended its consortium with WMSU-CN in March 2018, composed of four (4) regular or permanent with 2 M.A.N., and 1 in thesis writing in

MAN, and 1 RN. Currently, there are no contractual and part-time instructors. The school will request from administration to recruit / hire new faculty members and recall to hire the interested previous part-time faculty, based on required qualifications especially having academic preparation appropriate to their teaching assignments in order to suffice the demands of the School of Nursing as it shall evolve. There is a need of 4 part-time faculty members to augment the instruction especially, during the second semester, SY: 2018-2019 as the RLE (Skills Laboratory) of the students commences.

1.3. Library

Currently, the main library is managed by a registered librarian with its staff personnel and facilities and holdings are more likely conformed to existing CHED requirements. The need to upgrade and enhance the needed requirements will be done on a regular basis as a mandate of the College.

1.4. Laboratory and facilities

There are already established laboratories and facilities to be used by the students in compliance to guidelines in CMO 15, s. 2017. The establishment of the new laboratory building and purchase of needed materials and equipment will continuously be incorporated in the annual operational plan of the Sulu State College. Resources in the School of Nursing are shared to all year levels. These include the classroom, nursing skills laboratory, virtual nursing skills laboratory, and clinical facilities and resources among others.

1.4.1. Classroom

The Sulu State College School of Nursing has 2 story-building with 6 classrooms that can well accommodate a maximum of 40 students per room located safely and comfortably at the SSC main campus. Their science laboratory classrooms can accommodate a maximum 20 students which are located at the Science Building separate from the School of Nursing building

1.4.2. Nursing Skills Laboratory

The nursing skills laboratory of the School of Nursing is well-lighted and well-ventilated and also conducive to the demonstration and practice learning of students with adequate size as required in the CMO 15, s. 2017, so far. It is an amphitheater-style demonstration room that can accommodate a maximum of 40 students with lavatory and also water. It has 2 doors with basic equipment and supplies for demonstration of the students.

1.4.3. Virtual Nursing Skills Laboratory

The School of Nursing strongly requests and encourages the SSC administration their supports to put up an upgraded Virtual Skills Laboratory to supplement and complement the attainment of learning outcomes of the students prior to their actual experience or exposure.

14.4. Clinical Facilities and Resources

The clinical facilities of the School of Nursing in SSC for the RLE opportunities designed to develop the competencies of students utilizing processes in various health situations be continuously sourced from the different health institutions and agencies in and out of the Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu. They strive to establish linkages to these health institutions not only in terms of affiliation hospitals and units, but moreover accommodate an adequate and appropriate base hospital to be the prime clinical learning resource of the School of Nursing where a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) be secured, effective, and notarized.

1.5. Enrollment

SSC-SN caters students from Jolo and other municipalities in Sulu. The children of faculty member and staff of SSC can also be accommodated provided same requirements apply. Furthermore, following the guidelines stipulated in CMO 15, s. 2017, the SSC-SN accepts Grade 12 Senior High School graduates of the K-12 Curriculum and delimits enrollees of at least 80 students divided into two sections. These students must have a General Average of 85% and above, must pass the SSC College entrance examination, NAT examination and as well as interview evaluation set by the School of Nursing in coordination with the SSC Office of Admission.

Table 1. *Projected Number of Enrollees S.Y. 2018-2019*

First year	1st Semester	2nd Semester
No. of Enrollees	60	60
Total	60	60

Table 1 shows, a total of 60 students who are projected willing to enroll in SSC-SN based from the Nursing Aptitude Test (NAT) given May 16, 2018 in agreement with Asian Psychological Services and Assessment, Inc. (APSA Inc.), as primary requirement for admission into the program, although, more than hundreds are willing and took the NAT given.

1.6. Curriculum

The SSC-SN follows the BSN curriculum stipulated in CMO 15, s. 2017 which is an Outcome-Based Education (OBE). For the School year 2018-2019, it offers first year level, and the other grade levels be offered in the succeeding school years. The curriculum aligns with the institution's vision, mission, and goals.

The components of the curriculum implementation cover General Education Courses (GEC) with a total number of 36 units such as a) core courses, 24 units; b) Elective courses, 9 units; and c) Life and works of Rizal, 3 units. It shall also be composed of PE and NSTP 1 & 2, 14 units; major courses, 17 units, and moreover, professional courses with a total 125 units. Overall, the students shall complete the total number of 192 units. Furthermore, at the end of the BSN program, the recommended total number of

Related Learning Experiences (RLE), skills laboratory/clinical shall be completed and complied such as 53 RLE units with a total of 2,703 hours, of which 20-30% of the Total hours (540-810 hours) shall be allotted for Self-Directed Learning of the students. In addition, at the end of the BSN program also, the recommended total number of laboratory units of 7 units accounting to 357 hours (1 unit lab = 51 hours) shall be completed as well. A curriculum mapping of the program outcomes to the basic and major courses of the BSN curriculum prepared accordingly.

1.7. Budget

Since the School of Nursing has been established in 2004 up to the present, its budget will be continuously sourced out from the GAA of the College. Specifically, the payment of salaries and other compensation benefits of teaching and non-teaching personnel with plantilla item or position, including the funding requirements for the maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE) of the re-established SSC-SN shall be continuously be provided and incorporated in the General Appropriations Act (GAA). However, employees with contractual and part-time status will continuously have their salaries drawn from the income and saving of the school since it operates under self-liquidating mechanism.

Below is the budgetary requirement for the proposed BSN program in Sulu State College for School Year 2018-2019.

The data in Table 2 shows the breakdown of expenses in terms of personnel services, utility expenses, maintenance expenses, faculty development and personnel incentives has the annual rate of 2,085,552.00 with personnel services (regular faculty members) taking the most of the expenses. However, based on the faculty listing, all current faculty members have permanent status. There is a need to hire or recall part-time clinical instructors to service to augment the needs. To support the expenses on part-time faculty salary with Php28,000.00 for 5 months (since RLE starts to commence in the 2nd semester) that is Php140,000.00 with 4 needed part-time faculty. Below is the projected income for S.Y. 2018-2019. The salaries of Part-time faculty as clinical instructors handling the RLE of students will be taken from the RLE fees.

Table 2. *Projected Operating Expenses of the Proposed BSN for School Year 2018-2019*

Category	Monthly	Annually
A. Personnel Services	129,796.00	1,557,552.00
B. Utility Expenses	28,000.00	168,000.00
C. Maintenance Expenses	20,000.00	240,000.00
D. Faculty Development	10,000.00	120,000.00

E. Personnel Incentives (Bonus, PIB, Clothing, etc)	N/A	10,000.00
Grand Total		2,085,552.00

The data in Table 3 shows that with 60 enrollees for the 1st and 2nd semesters, SY: 2018-2019, it can generate fees collection of **Php762,840.00** which may able to support the salary of the part-time faculty (clinical instructors) as well as other expenses reflected in Table 2.

Table 3. *Projected Fees Collection Year 2018-2019*

Year Level	No. of Enrollees	1 st Semester		2 nd Semester		TOTAL	TOTAL AMOUNT
		Tuition Fees	RLE Fee	Tuition Fees	RLE Fees		
First Year	60	3,510.00	N/A	3,900.00	5,304.00	12,714.00	762,840.00
TOTAL							762,840.00

With the projected enrollees of 140 students as shown in Table 4, relative to the opening of classes for more year levels during the second year of operation, a total collection of **Php2,480,400.00** is expected to cover all the items in Table 2.

Table 4. *Projected Fees Collection for School Year 2019-2020*

Year Level	No. of Enrollees	1 st Semester		2 nd Semester		TOTAL	TOTAL AMOUNT
		Fees	RLE Fee	Fees	RLE Fees		
1 st Year	80	3,510.00	N/A	3,900.00	5,304.00	12,714.00	1,017,120.00
2 nd Year	60	3,510.00	9,282.00	3,640.00	7,956.00	24,388.00	1,463,280.00
TOTAL	140						2,480,400.00

With the projected enrollees of 220 students as shown in Table 5, due to opening of classes for more year levels during the third year of operation (2020-2021), a total collection of **Php 4,830,800.00** is expected to cover all the items in Table 2 with savings or income on the third year of operations. On the third year, it can be reflected that the school is already fully self –sustaining with savings or income earned.

Table 5. Projected Fees Collection for School Year 2020-2021

Year Level	No. of Enrollees	1 st Semester		2 nd Semester		TOTAL	TOTAL AMOUNT
		Tuition Fees	RLE Fee	Tuition Fees	RLE Fees		
1 st Year	80	3,510.00	N/A	3,900.00	5,304.00	12,714.00	1,017,120.00
2 nd Year	80	3,510.00	9,282.00	3,640.00	7,956.00	24,388.00	1,951,040.00
3 rd Year	60	2,990.00	11,934.00	2,860.00	13,260.00	31,044.00	1,862,640.00
TOTAL	220						4,830,800.00

With the projected enrollees of 300 students as shown in Table 6, due to opening of classes for more year levels during the fourth year of operation (2021-2022), a total collection of **Php7,028,400.00** is expected to cover all the items in Table 2.

Table 6. Projected Fees Collection for School Year 2021-2022

Year Level	No. of Enrollees	1 st Semester		2 nd Semester		TOTAL	TOTAL AMOUNT
		Tuition Fees	RLE Fee	Tuition Fees	RLE Fees		
1 st Year	80	3,510.00	N/A	3,900.00	5,304.00	12,714.00	1,017,120.00
2 nd Year	80	3,510.00	9,282.00	3,640.00	7,956.00	24,388.00	1,951,040.00
3 rd Year	80	2,990.00	11,934.00	2,860.00	13,260.00	31,044.00	2,483,520.00
4 th Year	60	3,250.00	10,608.00	1,820.00	11,934.00	27,612.00	1,656,720.00
TOTAL	300						7,108,400.00

With the projected enrollees of 320 students as shown in Table 7, due to opening of classes for more year levels during the fifth year of operation (2022-2023), a total collection of **Php7,660,640.00** is expected to cover all the items in Table 2.

Table 7. Projected Fees Collection for School Year 2022-2023

Year Level	No. of Enrollees	1 st Semester		2 nd Semester		TOTAL	TOTAL AMOUNT
		Fees	RLE Fee	Fees	RLE Fees		
1 st Year	80	3,510.00	N/A	3,900.00	5,304.00	12,714.00	1,017,120.00
2 nd Year	80	3,510.00	9,282.00	3,640.00	7,956.00	24,388.00	1,951,040.00
3 rd Year	80	2,990.00	11,934.00	2,860.00	13,260.00	31,044.00	2,483,520.00
4 th Year	80	3,250.00	10,608.00	1,820.00	11,934.00	27,612.00	2,208,960.00
TOTAL	320						7,660,640.00

Though there are an increment or increase of operating expenses per year as shown in Table 8, it can be seen that projected income by the third year, it can be already self-sustaining, meaning it can support all of its operational expenses.

Table 8. *Projected Operating Expenses for the Next Five (5) Years*

Year	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
Expenses (in pesos)	2,085,552.00	2,761,508.00	4,066,000.00	5,013,276.00	5,073,276.00

Table 9 shows the projected collection from tuition and RLE fees for SY: 2018-2023. It indicates an increase in fees collection every year as more adequate number of students are enrolled into the nursing program.

Table 9. *Project FEES Collection for the Next Five (5) Years*

Year	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
Collection (in pesos)	762,840.00	2,480,400.00	4,830,800.00	7,108,400.00	7,660,640.00

Table 10 gives a glimpse that during the first two years of operation of the program there is negative or no income earned (saved), in fact even deficit, however, since the salary of the regular/permanent faculty hired and to be hired can be augmented from the GAA of the institution, it can reflect positive outlook income. But, for the succeeding years relative to the increase of enrolment, it can be seen that there are already income that can be generated and all operational expenses may be already covered.

Table 10. *Projected Income for the Next Five (5) Years*

Year	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
Projected income	-1,322,712.00	-281,108.00	764,800.00	2,095,124.00	2,587,386

Table 11 provides summary "Collection," "Expenses," and "Income" for five the next five (5) Years (2018-2023). To understand how effectively the SSC School of Nursing is converting its collections into income, for the next five (5) years, profitability ratio, specifically, the Income as a Percentage of Collection = (Collection/Income) × 100% was further calculated.

The results showed, in 2018-2019, the profitability ratio is -173.40%. In this year, the School of Nursing can lose significantly more money than it collected. For every 100 pesos collected, it can incur 173.40 pesos in losses that indicates a very high operating cost relative to its revenue.

However, in 2019-2020, the profitability is -11.33%, while still a loss, the magnitude of the loss relative to collection has significantly decreased. For every 100 pesos collected, it can lose 11.33 pesos showing an improvement in cost management or an increase in revenue efficiency compared to the previous year. Moreover, in 2020-2021, the profitability ratio is 15.83% which marks a turning point for the School of Nursing, becoming profitable. For every 100 pesos collected, it can generate 15.83 pesos in income which indicates that the collections can be now sufficient to cover expenses and generate a profit. In 2021-2022, profitability ratio can significantly increase to 29.47%. For every 100 pesos collected, 29.47 pesos can be converted into income, which shows continued improvement in operational efficiency and stronger financial performance. Also, in 2022-2023, the highest profitability can be observed with 33.78%. For every 100 pesos collected, 33.78 pesos can be converted into income, indicating excellent financial health and strong management of expenses relative to collections.

Furthermore, the overall total profitability ratio for the Five Years is 16.83%. On average over the five years, the School of Nursing can generate 16.83% profit from its collections, hence this provides an overall picture of the financial performance for the entire period indicating its operational efficiency and financial success.

Table 11. Summary of Collection, Expenses and Income for the Next Five (5) Years

Year	Collection	Expenses	Income	Profitability Ratio
2018-2019	762,840.00	2,085,552.00	-1,322,712.00	-173.40%
2019-2020	2,480,400.00	2,761,508.00	-281,108.00	-11.33%
2020-2021	4,830,800.00	4,066,000.00	764,800.00	15.83%
2021-2022	7,108,400.00	5,013,276.00	2,095,124.00	29.47%
2022-2023	7,660,640.00	5,073,276.00	2,587,386.00	33.78%
Total	22,843,080.00	18,999,612.00	3,843,490.00	16.83%

Conclusion

Based from the examination and analysis of compliance in various areas crucial to the operation of the program, the re-establishment of offering of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) in Sulu State College for the School year 2018-2019 and beyond is feasible and viable. Given the overall total profitability ratio

for the Five Years of 16.83%, the School of Nursing can generate 16.83% profit from its collections indicating that their financial performance can achieve operational efficiency and financial success.

Therefore, with steady increase of enrolment, the BSN program in Sulu State College can be self-sustaining by its third year of operation and onward. Its institutional fees collection can be enough to fully cover operational expenses with income by the third year onward of its operation.

Recommendations

Based from the findings, the following are further recommended:

1. The re-establishment of offering of BSN in Sulu State College for the School year 2018-2019 and beyond is feasible and sustainable, considering the availability of its existing infrastructures and resources, it is very significant milestone to revive the program to operate independently to continue to provide an affordable, accessible, quality nursing education thru challenge-driven commitment (CDC) in the pursuit of being a catalyst of change for health human resource development (HHRD) and socio-economic development locally, regionally, nationally and as far as globally.
2. The faculty members with permanent status may be assigned during the first and second year of its operation as there are only a few classes to be opened.
3. The implementation and operation of the BSN program in Sulu State College may, utmost, adhere and comply with the Policies and Standards and Guidelines stipulated in the CMO 15, s. 2017 and shall continuously commit to its mandates as Higher Education institution to ensure the success and sustainability of the program.

REFERENCES

Box, G. E. P., Jenkins, G. M., Reinsel, G. C., & Ljung, G. M. (2015). *Time Series Analysis:*

Forecasting and Control (5th ed.). Wiley.

Commision on Higher Education Memorandum Order (CMO). (2017). Policies, Standards, and Guidelines for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) Program. Retrieved from: <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CMO-15-s-2017.pdf>

Gitman, L. J., & Zutter, C. J. (2014). *Principles of Managerial Finance*. Pearson.

Moore, D. S., Notz, W. I., & Fligner, M. A. (2017). *The Basic Practice of Statistics*. W. H. Freeman and Company.

University and Campus reports (2013-2018):

Nursing Office, Planning Office, Admission Office; Human Resource Management, and Accounting Office.